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The temperature dependence of intermediate range oxygen-oxygen correlations in liquid water

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We analyze the recent temperature dependent oxygen-oxygen pair-distribution functions from experimental high-precision x-ray diffraction data of bulk water by Skinner *et al.* [J. Chem. Phys. **141**, 214507 (2014)] with particular focus on the intermediate range where small, but significant, correlations are found out to 17 Å. The second peak in the pair-distribution function at 4.5 Å is connected to tetrahedral coordination and was shown by Skinner *et al.* to change behavior with temperature below the temperature of minimum isothermal compressibility. Here we show that this is associated also with a peak growing at 11 Å which strongly indicates a collective character of fluctuations leading to the enhanced compressibility at lower temperatures. We note that the peak at ~13.2 Å exhibits a temperature dependence similar to that of the density with a maximum close to 277 K or 4 °C. We analyze simulations of the TIP4P/2005 water model in the same manner and find excellent agreement between simulations and experiment albeit with a temperature shift of ~20 K. © 2016 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). [<http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.4961404>]

I. INTRODUCTION

Water is unique in the number of properties that deviate from what would be expected for a normal, simple liquid.¹ The thermodynamic response functions—e.g., isothermal compressibility (κ_T) and isobaric heat capacity (C_P)—are here of particular interest since they can be related to density, respectively entropy, fluctuations in the liquid,² which increase, seemingly without bound,³ as the liquid is cooled below 46 °C (κ_T) and 35 °C (C_P). Clearly, the fluctuations responsible for this anomalous increase cannot be simple thermal fluctuations, but must be related to structural changes in the hydrogen-bonding (H-bonding) network in the liquid as H-bonding becomes increasingly important when the temperature is lowered.⁴

When discussing thermodynamic properties of water, such as the temperature- and pressure-dependence of κ_T , C_P , as well as, e.g., the density maximum at 4 °C, a picture of fluctuations between two different forms of the liquid is gaining ground. These two forms are typically denoted high-density liquid (HDL) and low-density liquid (LDL);^{4–29} HDL is favored by entropy and should thus dominate at higher temperatures while LDL is favored by enthalpy through tetrahedral H-bonding and grows in importance as the liquid is cooled.³⁰ Such a picture is also supported

by small-angle x-ray scattering (SAXS) measurements^{10,31} which directly probe instantaneous density inhomogeneities in the liquid. The interpretation in terms of fluctuating lower-density heterogeneities of spatial extent on the order of 1 nm diameter in ambient water¹⁰ was questioned^{32–36} but finds support both from simulations and from a statistical mechanics analysis.^{37–40} Performing SAXS measurements at lower temperatures showed that the spatial extent of the fluctuations grows with decreasing temperature,³¹ but the structure of such heterogeneities in terms of H-bonding cannot be obtained from SAXS.

X-ray scattering measurements on liquid water have recently seen significant developments^{41–44} in terms of container-free measurements as well as separation of elastic and Compton scattering which now allow a more detailed analysis of the structure in the liquid. Huang *et al.*⁴¹ combined wide-angle x-ray scattering (WAXS) with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to investigate the temperature dependence of the different peaks in the oxygen-oxygen pair-distribution function (O–O PDF). The fourth peak at 9 Å was found to shift to lower r and become increasingly more well-defined with decreasing temperature. Also the correlation at 11 Å (fifth shell) was found to become more well-defined at lower temperature. The MD simulations reproduced the temperature dependence near-quantitatively, which allowed a structural assignment of the peaks based on the local structure index (LSI)^{45,46} that discriminates between HDL- and LDL-like local environments. Both peaks were confirmed to be of LDL character and the shift of the peak around 9 Å was determined

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to result from HDL having a peak at somewhat longer distance such that, as the temperature was decreased and the relative importance of HDL and LDL changed, the resulting peak shifted to lower r .⁴¹

The main improvement in terms of x-ray scattering studies of water has been to use very high energy photons, which allows measuring significantly higher q -transfer using a single detector.^{42–44} With data going up to $q = 26 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, Skinner *et al.*⁴⁴ were able to demonstrate convergence in terms of position and height of the first peak in the O–O PDF with respect to the measured q -transfer. It was demonstrated that for convergence the structure factor needed to be measured out to a minimum $q \approx 18 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ and a resulting benchmark O–O PDF for ambient water with very small error bars was derived.⁴⁴

The data of Skinner *et al.*⁴² and Neufeind *et al.*⁴⁷ were not only taken for ambient water but covered the wide range of temperatures from 254.2 to 365.9 K such that now data exist and can be analyzed for a whole series of temperatures. In the analysis by Skinner *et al.*,⁴² the temperature dependence of the O–H and H–H partial correlations was found to have a vanishingly small effect on the O–O PDFs for $r > 3 \text{ \AA}$. Particular attention was focused on the behavior of the first two peaks in the O–O PDF as a function of temperature. The position of the first peak was shown to increase linearly with temperature, where the expansion is expected since above the density maximum the density decreases upon heating. The position of the second peak was found to mimic that of the first, but only up to the compressibility minimum at 319 K where the second peak changes behavior and rapidly moves to a longer distance and becomes less well defined. Since the second peak is connected to tetrahedral coordination in the liquid, this result is of great interest for understanding the structure of the liquid and the origin of its many anomalous properties. The minimum in the isothermal compressibility appears as a result of structural fluctuations taking over from normal thermal fluctuations as the liquid is cooled. In a two-state picture of water under ambient conditions^{5,8,10,11,28,29} these structural fluctuations are into local tetrahedral structures in an otherwise close-packed, disordered liquid, fully consistent with the data for the second peak which shows that tetrahedral H-bond coordination only becomes significant around the minimum in the isothermal compressibility.

The experiment by Skinner *et al.* resolves a temperature dependent shell-structure reaching to much larger distance than in earlier data. Indeed, even an eighth peak at $\approx 17 \text{ \AA}$ appears at the lowest temperatures in the experiment. The fourth and fifth peaks and their temperature dependence have been discussed earlier by Huang *et al.*⁴¹ As discussed above, these peaks are well reproduced⁴¹ in MD simulations using the TIP4P/2005 force-field⁴⁸ which allowed these peaks to be characterized structurally. These assignments are verified here but the quality of the present data and near-quantitative agreement between experimental and simulated PDFs allow conclusions to be drawn also regarding correlations at longer distances as well as on their structural origin.

Fig. 1 shows the O–O PDFs of water at $T = 254.2 \text{ K}$ and $T = 342.7 \text{ K}$ with the first three peaks clearly more pronounced at lower temperature. In the present work we will perform a

FIG. 1. O–O PDF obtained from x-ray diffraction measurements⁴² at $T = 254.2 \text{ K}$ (blue curve) and $T = 342.7 \text{ K}$ (red curve). In the present work we focus on the delicate features in the intermediate range of $r = 8\text{--}20 \text{ \AA}$, as indicated by the green box.

detailed analysis of the intermediate- to long-range features in the range of $r = 8\text{--}20 \text{ \AA}$, as indicated in Fig. 1, found in the O–O PDFs from the work of Skinner *et al.*⁴² where we will pinpoint the temperature-dependent structural changes and analyze in detail the origin of the different features.

II. METHODS

We analyze MD trajectories, obtained in a previous study,⁴¹ from simulations of the TIP4P/2005 model of water⁴⁸ with 45 000 molecules using the GROMACS⁴⁹ program package. These simulations were run in the NPT ensemble at a pressure of $P = 1 \text{ bar}$ for different temperatures in the range 253–360 K. Pressure and temperature were controlled using the Parrinello-Rahman barostat⁵⁰ and the Nosé-Hoover thermostat,^{51,52} respectively, and long-range electrostatic interactions were treated with the particle-mesh Ewald method.

The underlying molecular structures that give rise to certain features in the O–O PDFs can be analyzed in simulations. Here we use the LSI order parameter⁴⁵ to analyze MD trajectories at $T = 253 \text{ K}$ and $T = 298 \text{ K}$ structurally by separately generating O–O PDFs for molecules with very low LSI values (disordered, HDL-like local environment) or very high values (strongly tetrahedral, LDL-like local environment). The LSI value assigned to each molecule is calculated in the inherent structure⁵³ and we calculate the PDFs of the oxygen atoms of LSI-classified molecules in two different ways: either with all the oxygen atoms surrounding the classified one in the instantaneous real structure or as the PDFs only including oxygen atoms within the same class of LSI values. Since the simulation involved 45 000 molecules, we still have sufficient statistics even when finer divisions of the range of LSI values are considered. These PDFs over molecules in different ranges of LSI values should be interpreted as correlation functions and are not directly connected to local density since the classification is in terms of the LSI order parameter.

To illustrate the inhomogeneous distribution of molecules classified according to their LSI values, we calculate the LSI-field of individual snapshots of the simulation. This is done assigning to each oxygen a normalized Gaussian of coarse-graining length⁵⁴ $\xi = 2.1 \text{ \AA}$ that is multiplied by the corresponding LSI value. The Gauss-weighted contributions of all oxygens are summed up at each grid point of a $50 \times 50 \times 50$ spatial grid to obtain grid-LSI values which can then be visualized as grid-LSI iso-surfaces.

The O–O PDF data presented by Skinner *et al.* were obtained by Fourier transformation of the x-ray structure factors using an r -dependent window function as described in detail in Ref. 42. This procedure discriminates against high-frequency noise, essentially without broadening the significant structural features in the O–O PDFs.

Both the experimental and simulated PDFs were smoothed using Gaussian filtering,⁵⁵ where each data point in the smoothed PDF is obtained as the Gauss-weighted average over the original data points in a neighborhood of the position considered. The width of the Gaussian, that controls how many data points are averaged over, can be adjusted. The r -spacing of the experimental data is $\Delta r = 0.01 \text{ \AA}$, while the PDFs from simulations were calculated at $\Delta r = 0.02 \text{ \AA}$; the difference in resolution is a matter of convenience and does not affect the results. Here, we use a Gaussian width of about 1.5 \AA , i.e., we average the experimental data over 150 data points and the simulation data over 74 data points, respectively. We tested a Gaussian filtering at a width of 0.6 \AA and while the height of the features in the PDF changes, the qualitative results and trends are independent of the Gaussian width. With the analysis of the qualitative changes with temperature in focus we chose the harder Gaussian filtering at a Gaussian width of 1.5 \AA and use the same filtering for all PDFs presented.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the filtering procedure described in Sec. II, we obtain smooth PDFs in both the experimental and simulated data as shown in Fig. 2. We note first that the excellent overall agreement between experimental and simulation data rules out that the features found are artifacts from the Fourier transform of the experimental data or noise. All features found in the experimental data are also present in the simulation data.

The temperature scale is shifted when comparing experiment and simulations, clearly seen for the highest temperatures, which is in agreement with the phase diagram of TIP4P/2005 being shifted in temperature: while the model reproduces the temperature of maximum density near-quantitatively at $T_{\text{max}} = 278 \text{ K}$,⁴⁸ its melting point has been reported to be $T_{\text{m}} = 252 \text{ K}$ ⁴⁸ and the boiling point $T_{\text{b}} = 401 \text{ K}$,⁵⁶ i.e., shifts of the order 20–30 K resulting in an overestimated temperature difference between T_{m} and T_{b} . However, allowing for these shifts in temperature we find an excellent agreement in Fig. 2 between the TIP4P/2005 temperature-dependent PDFs and experiment which allows using the simulations to analyze the experimental PDFs in some detail. In Fig. 3 we show the decomposition of the PDFs

FIG. 2. Intermediate range of O–O PDFs extracted from (a) experiment and (b) simulations of the TIP4P/2005 model of water. The range between $r = 14$ and 20 \AA is magnified in the insets. Reprinted with permission from D. Schlesinger, “Molecular structure and dynamics of liquid water — Simulations complementing experiments,” Ph.D. thesis, Stockholm University, 2015.⁶³

in terms of extremes in LSI values; a more finely decomposed picture is given in Figs. S1 and S2 of the [supplementary material](#).

Beyond the third shell we observe temperature-dependent peaks with positions at $r_4 \approx 9 \text{ \AA}$, $r_5 \approx 11 \text{ \AA}$, $r_6 \approx 13 \text{ \AA}$, $r_7 \approx 15 \text{ \AA}$, and $r_8 \approx 17 \text{ \AA}$ and define their respective heights accordingly as g_4 – g_8 . At higher temperatures and for increasing distance, the features naturally become harder to identify and the uncertainties increase. Nevertheless, the changes with temperature can be clearly identified and show the same qualitative behavior in the experimental and simulation data.

We note that, similar to Ref. 41, also in the present data the feature r_4 moves towards lower r with decreasing temperature and initially becomes broader, but that below 260 K it becomes very sharp with a rapid increase of the height. The shift and broadening are in agreement with the earlier analysis⁴¹ where more LDL-like local environments result in an r_4 peak at a shorter distance than the corresponding HDL-like. The broadening and movement towards shorter distance followed by the increase in height and sharpness are then natural consequences of the varying weight of contributions from both HDL and LDL, together with LDL being structurally

FIG. 3. PDFs calculated for species with LSI values that are very low ($<0.035 \text{ \AA}^2$, HDL-like), very high ($>0.165 \text{ \AA}^2$, LDL-like) with *all* surrounding oxygens and the PDFs between species only within the LSI-selection (denoted respectively “all” and “select”). The temperature is (a) 253 K and (b) 298 K. Note the different scales for $g_{OO}(r)$ in (a) and (b). The insets show the long-range features between $r=12$ and 20 \AA magnified to resolve the delicate correlations.

more well-defined.⁴¹ This is clearly seen in Fig. 3 where for very low LSI values we observe a sharp peak around 9.5 \AA while for very high LSI values the peak is found around 8.5 \AA . The PDF for molecules with LSI values in the range between these extremes exhibits only weak correlations in this region. The continuous development of the peaks in this region as function of LSI value is shown in Figs. S1 and S2, where the transition between the two sharp extremes is clearly seen.

The height g_5 of feature r_5 at $\approx 11 \text{ \AA}$, Fig. 4(a), shows a strong temperature dependence and has previously been analyzed in detail.⁴¹ This feature starts to emerge upon cooling around the temperature of minimum compressibility, while the onset is seen to occur at higher temperatures in the simulation data. Furthermore, it grows in an accelerated fashion, with this trend somewhat more pronounced in the experimental data. The peak has been previously assigned to LDL-like structures with the increasing height thus indicating that the LDL fraction in the liquid increases and becomes more well-defined upon cooling below the temperature of minimum compressibility. We note further that this peak appears as the second shell at $r \sim 4.5 \text{ \AA}$ begins to become more well-defined and thus provides a strong indication of the collective character

FIG. 4. Heights of the intermediate range features g_5 (a), g_6 (b), and g_8 (c) as functions of temperature from experiment (red circles) and simulations (black triangles). The absolute heights depend on the smoothening which therefore has been applied in exactly the same way to experimental and simulation data. Reprinted with permission from D. Schlesinger, “Molecular structure and dynamics of liquid water — Simulations complementing experiments,” Ph.D. thesis, Stockholm University, 2015.⁶³

leading to fluctuations into nanometer-size LDL-like regions as suggested earlier based on SAXS data and simulations.¹⁰

The funnel-like region of anomalous structural fluctuations⁴ is associated with an apparent divergent point (ADP) in a liquid-liquid transition. The boundary is then defined as the onset of anomalous behavior in response functions such as the isothermal compressibility which in Ref. 42 has been shown to be associated with the second shell becoming more well defined at a temperature of $T = 319 \text{ K}$. In this picture, the onset of structural fluctuations corresponds to entering the funnel region extending out from an ADP in the phase diagram; we prefer this nomenclature over liquid-liquid critical point (LLCP) since the essence is the instability and growth of structural fluctuations and not whether or not true criticality can develop on sufficiently long length-scales. In the simulation the onset of the r_5 peak appears at a higher temperature which, in this picture, means that the funnel region at ambient pressure is broader in the simulation than in the experiment and thus exhibits weaker structural fluctuations than in the experiment as is also evidenced by the simulated isothermal compressibility for the model.^{57,58}

FIG. 5. Comparison of $g_6(T)$ and $\rho(T)$ from experiment. Density data taken from Refs. 60 and 61. Reprinted with permission from D. Schlesinger, "Molecular structure and dynamics of liquid water — Simulations complementing experiments," Ph.D. thesis, Stockholm University, 2015.⁶³

The peak, r_6 , at about 13 Å, which we identify as the sixth coordination shell, exhibits an interesting temperature dependence which is closely reproduced in the simulations (Fig. 4(b)). The peak height goes through a maximum close to 277 K, and the shape of its temperature dependence is surprisingly similar to that of the density, see Fig. 5. The change in the density with decreasing temperature with the occurrence of a maximum can be simply understood in terms of thermal fluctuations decreasing upon cooling, leading to an increase in density, while structural fluctuations into more open, LDL-like local molecular arrangements become increasingly favorable which makes the change in the density reverse to decrease below 277 K. In terms of the r_6 peak we note from Fig. 3 that species with high LSI value contribute only insignificantly to this peak (see also Figs. S1 and S2). The temperature dependence and close match with the density

FIG. 6. LSI field calculated on a $50 \times 50 \times 50$ grid for representative snapshots at (a) $T = 253$ K and (b) $T = 298$ K. The 3-dimensional iso-surfaces (left) indicate grid-LSI values of 1.7 (low, colored red) and 3.0 (high, colored blue) for both temperatures. Corresponding volume slices, i.e., cuts through the volume representations, are shown on the right with length scales indicated on the axes and a detailed color scale indicating the grid-LSI values. The iso-surfaces were rendered with VMD.⁶²

can then be understood as that, since the peak is dominated by HDL species, it becomes more and more well-defined, and thus sharper with increasing height g_6 , as the liquid is cooled. However, since LDL contributes insignificantly to this peak, the peak starts to go down in height as the fraction of HDL decreases and the fraction of LDL increases and begins to dominate around the density maximum.

At a distance of $r_7 \approx 15$ Å we observe the emergence of a weak feature at the lowest temperature measured; this feature is also seen as clearly emerging in the simulation. In the experimental data, the peak seems to grow out of the sixth coordination shell, while it is more emphasized in the simulation data. The appearance of this feature is found to coincide with that of the fourth peak around 8.5 Å and, similar to r_4 , also r_7 is directly associated with the highest LSI values (Fig. 3 and Figs. S1 and S2). It appears only at the lowest temperature and is thus clearly connected to the growth of collective tetrahedral fluctuations out to around 15 Å.

Finally, a very weak feature between 16 and 17.5 Å can be identified, here denoted r_8 . Fig. 4(c) shows the height g_8 as a function of temperature. The slope of the linear fit is very different for experimental and simulation data but the uncertainty is very large in this region due to the weakness of the peak and the high noise level. We can nevertheless state that this feature is observed to shift significantly to larger r upon decreasing temperature. From the LSI analysis both molecules with high and low LSI values contribute in this region but at different distances. Thus, as the balance between HDL- and LDL-like local structures shifts with temperature, the weak feature is seen to shift due to the redistribution of molecules between the two classes.

We can connect the above analysis to the pressure dependence of these peaks as recently measured using x-ray diffraction of water at pressures of up to 360 MPa.⁵⁹ With increasing pressure the peaks (r_2 , r_5), in the present work assigned as tetrahedral based on their temperature dependence and LSI values, go down in height and vanish at the highest pressure and ambient temperatures. In contrast, the r_4 peak becomes sharper, since the LDL-like contribution is eliminated, and also the r_6 peak becomes more dominated by HDL contributions and consequently sharper.

Fig. 6 illustrates the underlying instantaneous structure of typical snapshots from simulations at 253 K (Fig. 6(a)) and 298 K (Fig. 6(b)). The grid-LSI field (see Sec. II) is visualized as iso-surfaces for grid-LSI values of 1.7 (red) and 3.0 (blue) for both temperatures. We observe that the simulation snapshot at 253 K contains a much larger population of high grid-LSI values than the simulation snapshot at 298 K. The inhomogeneity in terms of the grid-LSI classification is evident and additionally illustrated in volume slices to the right of Fig. 6. The axes indicate characteristic length scales of the instantaneous inhomogeneities of the order 1 nm at 298 K and considerably larger patches of the high grid-LSI population at 253 K. The color scale indicates the gradual spatial change of grid-LSI character.

The LSI characterization we use here takes per definition only into account other molecules out to 3.7 Å.^{45,46} We can, however, conclude that a very structured (high LSI) or very disordered (low LSI) environment reaches even beyond the

range included in the characterization since correlations can be seen to be stronger among similarly LSI-classified molecules than in the PDFs involving all others. This is consistent with Fig. 6 where the central regions of the HDL and LDL granularities are more strictly defined than the outer regions and can thus be expected to give more distinct contributions to the specific type of correlation. Molecules with intermediate LSI values can then be regarded as being more in the outer parts of such correlated regions where the PDF averages over both types of ordering, i.e., high and low LSI.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the present investigation we analyze experimental liquid water O–O PDFs in a wide temperature range for intermediate and long range features. Comparison with data obtained from simulations using the TIP4P/2005 model of water shows near-quantitative agreement for the features beyond the first shell after taking into account a temperature offset of around 20 K. We analyze the structural changes with varying temperature from simulations in terms of contributions from instantaneous high- and low-LSI species, i.e., molecules in tetrahedral respectively disordered local environment.

The structural changes around $r = 11$ Å characterized by Huang *et al.*⁴¹ as due to tetrahedral structures, the appearance of a maximum of the height g_6 of the sixth peak at $r_6 \approx 13$ Å as a function of temperature, the emergence of a seventh coordination shell growing out of this shell on the long- r side, and the outward shift of the eighth peak at $r_8 \approx 17$ Å all reflect a rather dramatic re-structuring of the liquid upon cooling. These structural changes set in already at the temperature of minimum compressibility of $T = 319$ K as indicated by the rather sharp rise of the r_2 and r_5 peaks at 4.5 and 11 Å. This is in full agreement with small-angle x-ray scattering measurements that showed inhomogeneities of the bulk liquid on a scale of 1 nm at ambient temperature;¹⁰ the extremely short x-ray interaction time effectively results in snapshots of instantaneous molecular structures. As the temperature is lowered further to 250 K in the experiment, a new correlation appears at $r_7 \approx 15$ Å which is assigned as LDL-like, i.e., tetrahedral and with high LSI value. This is consistent with the picture of structural regions of molecules changing between HDL- and LDL-like local configurations, which we refer to here as fluctuations. At high temperatures, the liquid is dominated by the HDL-like, disordered species with fluctuations into local tetrahedral, LDL-like fluctuations becoming increasingly dominant as the temperature is lowered. There must naturally be a size distribution of the spatial extent of such fluctuations and the appearance of the correlation r_7 at low temperature should be interpreted as the size distribution shifting towards larger sizes such that the growing tetrahedral population begins to contribute more significantly. We note that the most well-defined contributions, i.e., sharper peaks should be due to molecules located more centrally in the fluctuations such that the averaging is more over molecules in similar environment. Molecules more at the border between LDL- and HDL-like regions in the fluctuations will average more over different

classes of molecules and thus have broader peaks as is clearly seen from the LSI-dependent peaks in Figures S1 and S2 in the [supplementary material](#).

We note, finally, the close correspondence with the picture of a funnel-like region of fluctuations of increasing magnitude as one moves along an isochore through the one-phase region beyond an apparent divergent point in the P-T diagram.⁴ It is of fundamental importance that this funnel-like region with structural fluctuations extends all the way up into the ambient region and that tetrahedrality can so clearly be followed through the temperature- and pressure-dependent PDFs as it begins to develop through structural fluctuations, but only below a temperature of around 319 K.⁴²

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

See the [supplementary material](#) for the intermediate range pair-distribution functions calculated within small intervals of the LSI value at $T = 253$ K (Fig. S1) and $T = 298$ K (Fig. S2).

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